

Qualification level, mental state and manifestation of cognitive functions in young soccer players

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14921550>

Abstract

A forced approach to the formation of the training system leads to negative consequences for the athlete's body, a decrease in special performance and deterioration in training results. The study of human behavior styles with cognitive activity allows us to take into account the understanding of the individual stability of psychophysiological characteristics: information perception, features of its processing, efficiency of problem solving and independent decision-making. The aim of the work was to determine the relationship between the components of the psychophysiological state of soccer players of different age groups. The study was conducted on 17 soccer players (13 years old) of the Tashkent Football Academy and 15 soccer players (15 years old) of the Uzbekistan national team under 15 years old using the psychodiagnostic complex "Multipsychometer-05". Analysis of the indicators of the functional mobility test of nervous processes showed an average level of the speed of assimilation of the skill of performing a new task, a below-average level of throughput, an average level of the minimum intersignal interval reflecting the maximum (maximum) speed of information processing, reflexivity and impulsivity parameters are balanced, but there is a tendency for the indicators to shift towards reflexivity. Analysis of the values that determine the predominance of the physical (symbolic) form of encoding over the semantic (semantic) form showed that skilled football players have a dominance of the right hemisphere.

Keywords: soccer players, mental state cognitive functions

Introduction

At the present stage of sports development, there is an increase in psycho-emotional and physical stress to a critical level (EbadiAsl et al. 2024; Dwihandaka et al., 2025). The tendency is to increase training time, volume of performance and the addition of various types of preparedness to sports activities.

The main topic in the preparedness system in sports, according to psychophysiological researchers: control and correction of the training process, taking into account the individual characteristics of athletes (Korobeynikov et al., 2022; Iskra et al., 2024).

A forced approach to the formation of a training system leads to negative consequences for the athlete's body, a decrease in special performance and a deterioration in training results (Lyzogub et al., 2017; Shynkaruk et al., 2025).

Scientific sources allow us to conclude that specialists working with elite athletes use a large amount of theoretical and empirical materials related to readiness for sports achievements (Nagorna et al., 2023). The studied materials showed a high level of physical and mental costs in highly qualified athletes during sports activities. Therefore, the development of a comprehensive control of long-term training of highly qualified athletes is an important task of the modern scientific approach.

The psychophysiological state of the athlete's body is an important property of the process of forming a functional system that determines success in each sport (Korobeynikov et al., 2020). The main component of the psychophysiological state is the personal properties of athletes: mental condition, intellectual potential, speed of thinking, attention and perception (Soylu et al., 2021)

Therefore, when dividing payers into National Teams, it is necessary to conduct a scientific analysis of the psychophysiological state of each of the persons. Also, all the information obtained should be provided to the coaching council for use in adjusting training programs (Clayson 2024; Kozina et al., 2019; Psychophysiological state determined by emotional and mental abilities of self-regulation in training and competitions (Pranoto et al., 2024)

The tradition of the psychophysiological state is associated with the individual-typological characteristics of athletes (Clayson 2024; Marder et al., 2024; Slade et al., 2024). But the results of human activity can affect not only the stability of personal properties, but also the temporary reactions of the body that determine the psychoemotional state of a person (Korobeinikova et al. 2024). Psychophysiological states have three levels of response: mental

(stress, anxiety), physiological (reaction of the autonomic nervous system) and behavioral. (Korobeynikov et al., 2022).

Study of human behavior styles with cognitive activity give account the understanding of individual stability of psychophysiological characteristics: perception of information, features of its processing, effectiveness of problem solving and independent decision-making. Identification of unique strategies in sports is one of the priority areas of sports science. In addition, some researchers have shown that psychophysiological functions and their properties have a genetic level of manifestation in ontogenesis (Brandão et al., 2023).

The aim of the work

Determination of the relationship between the components of the psychophysiological state of soccer players of different age groups.

Material and methods

To assess the current psycho-emotional state, an adaptive version of 8 colors from the Luscher test was used. Researchers and developers found that the choice of color scheme depended on the current state of personal characteristics that are associated with morphological features and other individual properties of a person. In addition, the choice of color affected the current mental state (Pranoto et al., 2024).

To assess the balance of excitation and inhibition processes of the nervous system, a test with spatio-temporal extrapolation "reaction to a moving object" was used. Variable accuracy characterized the level of ability for spatial anticipation and information processing. Variable stability indicated the level of balance of the nervous system. Variable anxiety, which demonstrated predominant excitation of nervous processes, was also assessed.

The Raven's Progressive Matrices test is characterized by high reliability and includes 12 matrices. This test demonstrates attention, perception and cognitive abilities. The test tasks consisted of choosing the missing element of the matrix from 6-8 proposed options. This test has a time limit (6 min). The following variables were evaluated as the outcome test: productivity, speed of information processing, accuracy and effectiveness. Statistical analysis was performed using non-parametric method (median, upper and lower quartiles) and correlation (Spearman) using the software "Statistica 12".

Participants

The study was conducted on 17 soccer players (13 years old) of the Tashkent Football Academy and 15 soccer players (15 years old) of the Uzbekistan National Team U15 using the psychodiagnostic complex "Multipsychometer-05".

Results

The results of the Luscher color diagnostics allow for an individual assessment and professional recommendations on how to avoid psychological stress and the physiological symptoms it causes. In addition, the Luscher test provides additional information for psychotherapy. The analysis of the study showed the average level for all variables in the Luscher test among both groups of soccer players. Table 1 presents the results of the Luscher test for 13- and 15-year-old soccer players. This table presents the following mental condition of football players: mental capacity, fatigue, anxiety, deviations from the autogenic norm, eccentricity, concentricity, vegetative coefficient, heteronomy, and autonomy.

Table 1 Psycho-emotional state of soccer players of different age groups (Luscher test, n=32)

Variables	Soccer players 15 years old (n=15)	Soccer players 13 years old (n=17)
Mental capacity, conditional unit	8,12 7,08; 10,30	10,63* 7,86; 12,00
Fatigue, conditional unit	4,32 2,11; 4,41	4,48 2,72; 5,48
Anxiety, conditional unit	3,08 2,21; 5,32	2,52 1,54; 3,55
Deviations from the autogenic norm, conditional unit	22,42 16,87; 24,9	16,48* 12,37; 22,05
Eccentricity, conditional unit	6,90 5,20; 8,28	10,28* 5,84; 11,88
Concentricity, conditional unit	8,06 6,15; 9,23	8,57 6,58; 11,48
Vegetative coefficient, conditional unit	19,23 16,42; 21,55	17,53* 13,42; 19,59
Heteronomy, conditional unit	6,14 4,26; 8,30	7,69* 5,48; 9,11
Autonomy, conditional unit	8,18 7,05; 9,75	10,21* 8,58; 11,09

Legend: * $p = .05$, comparison of two groups of soccer players

According to the results, the mental capacity of young 13-year-old soccer players has a reliable increase compared to other groups. The level of fatigue and anxiety does not differ significantly between both groups of soccer players.

The variable of deviations from the autogenic norm indicates a subjective characteristic of the assessment of mental comfort or discomfort. This variable is significantly lower in 13-year-old soccer players. This indicates a state of comfort in this group of soccer players.

The variable of eccentricity is lower in 15-year-old soccer players. This fact correlates with a decrease in mental capacity and indicates a deterioration in the psychoemotional state.

The values of the variable of the vegetative coefficient show a balance between the sympathetic and parasympathetic divisions of the autonomic nervous system. Higher values of this variable are shown in young 15-year-old soccer players. This indicates the predominance of sympathetic regulation in their soccer players.

When studying the psychophysiological state, it is necessary to take into account the informative parameters and the level of their expression. A number of functional system criteria that influence training results can be attributed to the psychophysiological mechanisms of the athlete's cognitive activity. The great importance are assessments of the styles of perception and processing of information at the level of decision-making in athletes.

The cognitive sphere combines the general ability to learn and solve problems depending on the level of expression of cognitive performance. The nature and results of cognitive abilities are assessed by quantitative (productivity and speed of completing tasks) and qualitative (accuracy and efficiency of solving tasks) parameters.

To study the general cognitive performance of skilled soccer players, the Reven test was used. Table 2 presents the results of the general cognitive (intellectual) performance of soccer players.

Table 2 The results of general cognitive (intellectual) performance (by test Raven) of soccer players with different age groups (n=32)

Variables	Soccer players 15 years old (n=15)	Soccer players 13 years old (n=17)
Productivity, conditional unit	7,00 5,10; 8,45	5,31* 5,53; 9,5
Speed of information processing, number stimulus/min	3,70 2,52; 5,71	3,11 2,84; 5,04
Accuracy, conditional unit	0,58 0,42; 0,72	0,42* 0,41; 0,75
Effectiveness, conditional unit	37,94 13,89; 48,40	13,89* 13,88; 53,57

Legend: * $p = .05$, comparison of two groups of soccer players

Productivity, accuracy and efficiency are better in the 15-year-old soccer players. This result demonstrated the predominance of quantitative characteristics of non-verbal intelligence among this group of soccer players. This may be a sign of a higher level of morphofunctional development in the 15-year-old group compared to the 13-year-old group. In addition, this fact indicates a lack of understanding among coaches of the need to develop non-verbal and other types of intelligence in skilled soccer players. The main characteristic of the effectiveness of game activity in soccer is spatio-temporal extrapolation. The moving object reaction test demonstrated this property. For all soccer players, significant differences between the two groups showed prevalence of excitation. This fact indicates that the 15-year-old soccer players have a predominance of excitation over inhibition.

Table 3 Results of the "Reaction to a moving object" test in soccer players of different age groups (n=32)

Variables	Soccer players 15 years old (n=15)	Soccer players 13 years old (n=17)
Accuracy number of mistakes	2,51 2,23; 2,75	2,96 2,49; 3,34
Stability, conditional unit	3,72 3,47; 4,20	3,95 3,59; 4,46
Arousal, conditional unit	-0,01 -0,08; 0,31	0,02* -0,08; 0,47

Legend: * $p = .05$, comparison of two groups of soccer players

The obtained results revealed that low mental capacity and the presence of mental discomfort are associated with excitation of the nervous system in soccer players.

To study the relationships between the psycho-emotional state, neurodynamics and cognitive functions, a correlation analysis was carried out (according to Spearman). The main variables with the studied correlation relationships are the characteristics of the Luscher test. This justifies the priority of the psycho-emotional state in the behavioral response of athletes (Aminovich et al., 2022).

The psycho-emotional state in the group of young soccer players aged 13 has a different vector direction. The number of correlation links in soccer players of this group more than

different group. We obtained the same results for the correlation between intellectual abilities and mental characteristics (Table 4).

The psycho-emotional state of young soccer players aged 15 has correlation links with the balance of excitation and inhibition of the nervous system (Table 5). No links with intellectual characteristics were found in this group.

Table 4 Correlation between psycho-emotional state and tests on cognitive properties in soccer player 15 year old

Indicators	Test Raven			Test anticipation		
	Productivity	Accuracy	Effectiveness	Accuracy	Stability	Arousal
Mental capacity	0,49	0,50	0,47	-0,45	-0,31	-0,30
Fatigue	-0,09	-0,09	-0,10	0,01	0,40	0,39
Anxiety	-0,56	-0,57	-0,55	0,38	0,33	0,24
Deviations from the autogenic norm	-0,40	-0,41	-0,35	0,29	0,17	0,44
Eccentricity	0,29	0,30	0,30	-0,42	-0,34	-0,46
Concentricity	-0,10	-0,10	-0,11	0,25	0,14	0,48
Vegetative coefficient	-0,13	-0,13	-0,06	0,01	-0,001	-0,11
Heteronomy	0,56	0,57	0,51	-0,26	-0,15	0,08

Legend: the highlighted values are reliable (p =.05)

Table 5 Correlation between psycho-emotional state and neurodynamic functions in soccer player 15 year old

Indicators	Productivity	Speed of information processing	Accuracy	Effectiveness
Mental capacity	-0,20	0,05	-0,21	-0,42
Fatigue	-0,52	0,09	-0,52	-0,32
Eccentricity	0,35	-0,41	0,35	0,14
Vegetative coefficient	0,38	0,24	0,35	0,41
Heteronomy	-0,29	0,06	-0,34	-0,53

Legend: the highlighted values are reliable (p =.05)

The obtained analysis showed that significant correlation coefficients indicate functional relationships between components, manifestation of the hierarchy of cause-and-effect relationships.

Discussion

A number of authors concluded that the properties of nervous processes are genetically determined (Makarenko et al., 2011; Lizogub et al., 2017; Korobeynikov et al., 2022). This theory is of great importance for developing ideas about the psychophysiological characteristics of human activity.

According to the authors, the balance of nervous processes characterizes the general energy level of the brain and the human body (Makarenko et al., 2011). The predominance of excitation of the nervous system is a manifestation of the style of behavior and personal mental properties (Auezovich et al., 2024).

The analysis of the results of the examination of athletes using the computer system of psychophysiological diagnostics "Multipsychometer-05", aimed at determining the indicators of individual-typological properties of the nervous system of athletes and allows us to state that skilled soccer players have an average level of accuracy and a below-average level of stability of reaction to a moving object.

Analysis of the results shows that all young soccer players have an average level of accuracy and a low level of stability of reaction to a moving object. Characteristic results are the predominance of excitation processes over inhibition processes, revealed with a decrease in the ability to anticipate in young soccer players. The results obtained are consistent with the data of some authors who have shown a decrease in the ability to perceive and anticipate in athletes with high levels of anxiety (Murphy et al, 2024; Mathur et al., 2024).

The analysis of the functional mobility of nervous processes showed that young soccer players have an average level of skill acquisition speed and a low level of visual performance with a high level of information processing speed. In addition, a tendency towards reflexivity of the nervous system was noted.

It was found that according to the indicators of cognitive abilities, young football players have an average level of productivity, speed and accuracy (quality) of non-verbal tests.

Deviations from the autogenic norm and the vegetative coefficient in young football players are balanced. Bipolar characteristics: eccentricity-concentricity, heteronomy-autonomy demonstrate a tendency towards a decrease in autonomy and the predominance of heteronomy in young soccer players.

Analysis of the predominance of physical over semantic forms of brain codes revealed the dominance of the right hemispheres in soccer players.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be noted that when studying the features of the manifestation of the psychophysiological state, it is necessary to study all levels of its components and draw conclusions about the state of a person based on a set of informative indicators describing each level.

Thus, the analysis of the indicators of the "Reaction to a moving object" test showed that in young soccer players, excitation processes prevail over inhibition processes, an individually specific level of activation prevails, which significantly affects the individual style of play of skilled football players. Therefore, the results of the non-verbal intelligence test in football players are low, and this indicates that coaches are not sufficiently aware of the development of non-verbal intelligence in players.

All tactical training should be based on verbal and non-verbal intellectual skills for maximum success of the entire team in a soccer game.

It was revealed that there is a connection between the psycho-emotional state, neurodynamic characteristics and non-verbal intelligence in young soccer players. The subjective mental state, the ability to make independent decisions leads to the balancing of nervous processes and helps soccer players quickly and effectively receive and process non-verbal information.

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